

Age distribution Austria vs. Vienna

Data Collection

What data will you collect or create?

During the experiment data about the distribution of Austrias and Viennas population by age is created. The original Data is coming from open data sites and are in tsv or csv format. The total input data is smaller than 2 MB. Therefore, it's easily possible to share.

The created tables of the experiment are getting saved as csv and the additional diagrams (line and bar chart) as png. I decided to use csv and png because they can be opened easily on every machine. It's also possible to share them because every os can read them. CSV specially guarantees to provide long term access because it's a simple text format.

The data collected is just a comparison of existing data therefore, the newly created is only additional information but doesn't need to be long term preserved. It's more important to preserve the original data so that the experiment is reproducible.

How will the data be collected or created?

The whole project is shared on github, which is used for versioning too.

The project is structured as follows, in the data/raw folder the input data/processed the raw output data is saved. Furthermore, there is a folder reports/ for saving the created diagrams. In the main folder the main script as well as the readme and docker files are located for reproducibility purposes. In the documentation folder there are metadata provided as well as an overview what has been done in the experiment.

Data creation:

The data will be created with python (jupyter notebook), specially pandas is used for processing the data and matplotlib.pyplot for plotting. During the processing only normal math is used to get the input data to a comparable format.

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Additional to the software the meaning of the values needs to be preserved so that the data can be interpreted in the future. To ensure that the values can be interpreted I will create a metadata document and furthermore a description document for the graphs.

The metadata Document will be XML based on the Dublin Core metadata schema. I used this format because it's the one which got presented during a lecture and I am therefore most familiarized with. It's also suited for documenting digital data like in this project involved.

The single processing steps are document in an additional Documentation file, including the architecture description.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

The data I am working with is already shared online without any privacy issues, they do not contain any personal data or personal information. I'm only processing the data and even abstract it more, therefore I can't see any privacy or ethical problems. The data I am working with are about the age of the population of specific regions, which is public and there is no harm expected by using the data for a comparison.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

- Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungprognose 2005-2035
The data is published from magistrate Wien, published under cc-by-4.0 license.
- Population by age group
The data is published from Eurostat. On their website they write "Eurostat has a policy of encouraging free re-use of its data, both for non-commercial and commercial purposes." therefore it should be cc-0.

I will publish my results under cc-by, to ensure that the traceability to the data of magistrate Wien is ensured.

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

Sufficient storage is available, in total the project is smaller than 5 MB.

The primary place where the project is stored is my laptop. Additionally, it will be stored in Github and the final data and source code is saved by Zendo with a DOI. If the data need to be recovered I (David Schmidt, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3129-6719>) will take care of it and clone it again from Github. Normally the

data will be backupd after each development process.

How will you manage access and security?

The risk to the data security is that some of the data gets changed and this is not noticed, to avoid this risk I will download the original data ones more after completing the project and verify the result. Furthermore, if the Project is finished the results get assigned a DOI as well as the source code and are therefore saved against manipulation. (10.5281/zenodo.2619280,10.5281/zenodo.2617382,10.5281/zenodo.2617376)

Access is controlled by git it's a public repository so that everyone can see it download it and to write I as owner of the repository have to agree to it.

If someone wants to collaborate it's easy to give him access by adding him as collaborator to the repository.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

There is no legal, contractual or regulatory purpose of the data. I will keep the data produced by the project, this is easily possible because of the small amount of data. The data will be guaranteed to preserved until the end of the summer term (1.7.2019), because afterwards it's not needed anymore for the lecture Data Stewardship.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

As mentioned before the data can be found on github (https://github.com/schmidii/data_experiment) and zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.2619280,10.5281/zenodo.2617382,10.5281/zenodo.2617376). There are no costs for the repository and there is also no additional time or real effort needed to prepare the preservation of it.

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

Potential users can find my data on github or Zenodo where I shared it with everyone. The data is going to be available immediately after the project is finished. I have a DOI for the data I produced as well as for the source code as mentioned before.

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

I will publish the data under cc-by-40 because also the data from the city of Vienna is published under this license, this data is the project based on.

There is no reason for me to exclusively use the data at any time and also a data sharing agreement is not required.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

As the only person involved (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3129-6719>), I am responsible for the data management of the produced experiment. For the input data Eurostat and the magistrate of Vienna is responsible to stare and backup.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

The data is produced with a python script, this will also be saved in the repository and with Zenodo. In the repository there is a readme with instructions how to reproduce the data.